

Effect of the Piezoceramic Embedment on the Robustness and Lamb Waves Transmission of Acoustic-Ultrasonic Composite Transducer (AUCT)

Shear-Lag Load transfer tuning

Ultimate strain determination

Piezoceramic pre-compression

Lamb wave performance characterization

Results resume

T _n	Transducer th. (mm)	Ultimate strain (%)	Max. amp. (mV)
T ₀ (ref.)	0.45	0.66	64
T ₁	0.65	0.88	42
T ₂	1	1.0	26
T ₃	1.35	1.2	15

Motivation

Fiber-reinforced composites are becoming more widely used with new materials and in new applications that require them to operate in highly loaded structures and at extreme temperatures. Acousto-ultrasonic composite transducers (AUCT) based on piezoceramic materials show great potential for monitoring damage in them. However, when they are integrated into highly loaded composite structures, their mechanical properties are challenging, particularly because they face brittleness and vulnerability to tensile loads. Therefore, increasing their tensile load tolerance and decreasing transferred stresses while attached into structures surfaces would allow them to be used in a wide range of composite applications.

Research hypothesis

- Thicker AUCT embedment results in a greater distance between the structure surface and the piezoceramic, which increases shear lag. Higher shear-lag causes less load transfer from the structure to the piezoceramic, allowing the AUCT to operate in higher loaded structures, increasing the robustness of the system
- Thicker AUCT embedment results in a greater pre-compression of the piezoceramic during the manufacturing process. Higher pre-compression allows the ceramic to survive to higher tensile loads, increasing the robustness of the system
- Thicker AUCT embedment can be used without compromising Lamb wave transmission performance

Results and discussion

- Ultimate strain survivability increases proportionally to the loss of performance on Lamb wave transmission.
- Despite significant signal decay, the Lamb wave's signal-to-noise ratio remains high, allowing the SHM analysis to be performed on all the proposed transducers
- Based on the findings, it is possible to identify optimal thickness configurations for specific applications where robustness is critical.

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